

A Study on Residual Axial Capacity of Impact Borne Reinforced Concrete Columns

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Abstract The paper discusses about the estimation of axial capacity of impact borne Reinforced Concrete (RC) column. The first attempt made and successful for real time experimental study and simulation of compression testing of RC columns after repetitive impact loads. The objective of this work is to estimate the residual axial capacity of RC columns damaged by different levels of repetitive impact loads. The exertion consisted of both experimental investigation and numerical simulation using finite element software. The FEM simulation was evaluated with the real time experimental data. An empirical factor was introduced which estimates the closeness of the numerical value with the experimental value. Based on the empirical factor, it was found that the both experimental and numerical values have good correlation on axial capacity of impact borne Reinforced Concrete column. The FEM simulation Abaqus software was used which assists us to find the stress accumulation zone in the RC column. The experimental studies, impact loads are created in the laboratory under load testing. Twenty RC columns were damaged by impact loads as well as axial compression testing were done. Among the 20 RC Columns four served for control and another four served for impact loads till ultimate failure. Remaining were divided as set of three and impact load was applied until various damage parameters developed under repetitive loading conditions. The post impact behavior along on load carrying capacity and failure pattern of RC columns were analyzed.

Keywords RC columns, Repetitive impact loadings, Axial capacity of columns, Finite element modelling, Residual strength of Columns.

Introduction

Due to advantages in terms of cost and functionality, square reinforced concrete (RC) columns have been widely utilized in the civil engineering constructions as the compression members. In which most of the RC Columns are designed for static and dynamic loads. The RC Columns situated in the low storey parking area are most vulnerable to the heavy vehicle impacts and the buildings RC Columns situated in the hilly and mountain regions are susceptible either to low velocity high mass rock fall impact or high velocity low mass rock fall impacts. These impact loads can also occur in the RC Columns of building during a land slide and earthquake under falling of the nearby buildings. Hence it is mandatory to study the post impact structural behavior of axially-loaded square RC columns under repetitive impacts. Impact load on the RC Columns leads to local damage to structural columns. This damage may extend further and leads to total failure of columns results in the overall collapse of the structures. This also mainly involves the huge cost involved in the repair and rehabilitation and the casualties. Most of the existing framed structures are at the service period of 50 – 60 years. In which further degradation of concrete and steel reinforcement due to the exposed atmosphere like Corrosion, Carbonation, Creep have already reduced the structural load carrying capacity of the elements. At this situation combined action of impact loads and concrete degradation property will make the structure to failure in brittle manner and the failure will be a catastrophic one. These dynamic loads may lead to a dynamic response result in the localized damage. These local damages will spread after the sudden loss the critical supporting elements, leading to the collapse of disproportionally large parts of structure as a result of inadequate design for the impact loads. Very few occurrences w.r.t failure of structures have observed under impact load it is much mandatory to address the issue as these failure leads to more casualties and economic burden in terms of repair, rehabilitation or sometimes reconstruction. The study of the failure mechanisms of the RC elements mainly the columns play a vital role in designing to resist the impact and other dynamic accidental loads in the future. To further continue the low velocity impact under repetitive condition will also severely affect the structure and may lead to total failure in case no proper repair and strengthening techniques are followed. In the recent times it is found that seismic pounding of two adjacent buildings induce impact load to the on fall nearby structures lead to total collapse of the building as failure of RC Column, in this scenario the seismic design adopted for the column goes null under the combined action of seismic and impact load simultaneously. This pounding effect mainly depends on the height and cross-sectional orientation of the building. Over the recent years research on reinforced concrete member subjected to low-velocity impact load and high velocity impact load have been the emerging field [13]. It is also found that the proper analytical simulation required is lagging and this simulation through proper software plays a vital role in reducing the time and large specimens' analysis at economy.

Problem Statement

Repetitive low velocity impact to building RC Column results in varying levels of damage and corresponding reduction in structural capacity. The degree of the damage limits the level of corrective maintenance required to keep the building in service or the decision to take proper repair techniques. However, little research has been carried out to study the damage levels resulting from intentional impact. Moreover, even less has been done to understand the residual loading

capacity of RC Column under low velocity repetitive impact. Unlike accidental impact, intentional impact results in higher levels of damage due to the acceleration, mass at the time of impact. A proper experimental study and analytical simulation is required to exactly know the post impact performance of RC Column.

Objective

- To identify the current state of the practice for the evaluation of post impact structural capacity of reinforced concrete columns.
- To analyze and identify the reliability of reinforced concrete columns subjected low velocity repetitive impacts.
- To experimentally investigate and analytically simulate the typical reinforced concrete columns to correlate the residual axial as a function of lateral low velocity repetitive impacts.
- To study the efficiency of the numerical model simulated using Finite element software.

Fig 1: Research Methodology

Experimental Investigation

The detailed experimental investigation done are discussed in this chapter. Totally 20 RC Column specimens were casted with 28 days compressive strength of concrete as 25N/mm². The RC column had 4 main longitudinal rebar of 12mm diameter and 8mm diameter rebar as stirrups with 100mm as c/c spacing with 150x150mm. Out of 20 RC Columns sets of 4 served as control and 4 for which repetitive impacts were given till severe damage. Remaining 12 were divided as sets of three and repetitive impacts were given till the damage of hairline, minor, major cracks, spalling and severe damage. After the damage all the RC Columns were structurally tested for axial compression testing using a 100T UTM.

Tests On Prototype Specimens

The column specimens will be tested towards impact loads by drop weight impact testings followed by uniaxial compression. The columns will be tested in a loading frame using a jack having capacity of 100T. Load increments will be applied uniformly. LVDT’s were used to measure the displacements.

Experimental Details

The ultimate aim of the project is to estimate the structural capacity of reinforced concrete after damaged by low velocity repetitive impact. Two stage experimental testing were performed. Initially the RC Columns were exposed to low velocity repetitive impact. Then the second stage was axial compression testing using the UTM of capacity 100T as per the latest calibration limit.

Specimen Details

The columns were casted with a little rusted main longitudinal reinforcement and fresh stirrups. This was done to simulate the site conditions. The proper necessary precautions were taken such the rusted reinforcement significantly does not play a major role on the structural strength reduction. The square RC Column with dimensions of 150x150x800mm with cover 25mm on either four sides was provided. The RC Column have #4 with diameter 12mm as main longitudinal reinforcement and stirrups of diameter 8mm with spacing 100mm c/c was provided. The yield strength of steel was 550Mpa. The main longitudinal reinforcements were rusted to small significance by immersing in 3% Nacl solution for a duration of 1344 hours. The proper precautions were taken that the reinforcement is not corroded. Un-rusted stirrups were used. Totally of 20 RC Columns were casted and grouped as a set of nos. 4 for control which were not exposed to the repetitive impact load and nos. 4 for severe damage due to impact. Remaining columns were grouped as a set of three which were exposed to impact till the attainment of Hair line, Minor, Major cracks and spalling. The number of impacts under repetitive conditions required for the damage were noted.

Fig 2: Detailing of RC Column

Impact Testing

The drop-weight method can test beams with a maximum span of 4 metres and up to 3 metres. The striker, which can be elevated up to 4m high, was guided by a frame with two vertical steel angle legs. The frame consisted of a pulley and an 8 kg spherical impactor. A steel wire rope attached was raised by the striker with the aid of a winch. The striker was released by turning off the wire plugger once it had reached the necessary height. The RC Column was tested towards the impact by placing the RC Column in horizontal layover. This was done to achieve the required the support conditions and the facility available in the laboratory for performing the low velocity repetitive impact test. The test set was built by taking the reference from impact testing set up [16]. Sixteen RC Columns were tested under the repetitive low velocity impacts. The impacts were given in the repetitive manner till certain amount of the damage were achieved. The repetitive impacts were given till the achievement of Hair line, Minor, Major cracks, Spalling and severe damage. The height of impact, Angle of impact, Weight of impact were kept constant throughout the experiment of 1500mm, 5000g, 90° respectively. The number of repetitive impacts were only the variable parameters as that depends mainly on the impacts required for the induced damage. Impact testing is performed to replicate the dynamic forces that packaged goods may encounter during transportation and handling. These forces are simulated using specialized impact test systems. In the case of inclined impact test systems, a carriage is employed to propel the test sample down a ramp at predetermined velocities, ultimately causing it to collide with a fixed backstop. By subjecting the specimen to these extreme conditions, engineers can assess its reaction and determine how it would perform in real-world supply chain scenarios. The columns were termed as the first letter “C” represents the column, The numerical “N” represent the trial number, The third letter “S” represent the study parameter and the last number “N1” represent the number of repetitive given to attain the damage.

Fig 3: Specimens Nomenclature.

Axial Compression Testing

The impact damaged RC Columns were tested for axial compression testing. Two LVDT's were kept adjacent to at the undamaged surface to monitor the displacement by the RC Column. Totally 20 RC Columns were tested, in which the four were control specimens tested for axial compression testing without any repetitive impact damage. The capacity of the UTM was 100T with height of level as 1m. The LVDT's are of range 10mm and 20mm which were kept at the adjacent sides. The machine was fully power hauled machine and load-based type. which mainly consisted of two fluid power systems: a horizontal hydraulic loading system for axial loading and a vertical hydraulic loading system for lateral loading.

Fig 4: Experimental Setup

Numerical Modelling of RC Column

The RC Column was modelled with the characteristics of modelling space as 3D with type as deformable along with basic feature shape as solid with extrusion type. The main longitudinal reinforcements and stirrups were modelled with modelling space 3D with type as deformable with basic feature of shape wire and type planner and with solid homogenous as section property. The coupling interaction was given for the top and bottom of the RC Column and Embedded region was given as the interaction property for the bond between steel and concrete. The conventional property termed as concrete damage plasticity model [CDP] was used for the concrete. The impactor was modelled as spherical in nature diameter of 150mm with weight of 8kg. The actual property parameter was modelled with low velocity of 5m/s. The bottom of the RC Column was fixed at the base hence the degrees of rotation in all 6 directions were restrained. The vertical displacement and reaction were measured at the loading point with implementation of reference point which was created at top on the vertical piece by a constraint tied at the reference point. A couple constraint which contains only transitional degree of freedom in mechanical simulations was provided between the concrete, reinforcement and stirrups assembly. Surface-to-surface contact interactions are the interactions between two deformable surfaces or a deformable surface and a rigid surface. Using the built-in SURFACE to SURFACE CONTACT command Explicit was used to define the contact between all model elements. The normal direction of contact between two surfaces was defined as a firm contact, whereas the tangential direction was defined by friction for contact between ceiling tiles and grid members. The top to bottom structured mesh was used for simulation. Top-down meshing relies on the geometry of a component to define the mesh's perimeter. The top-down mesh corresponds to the geometry. Needed to be simplified and/or partition complex geometry so that CAE can recognize fundamental shapes that it can use to generate a high-quality mesh. A mesh size of 50mm was selected for impactor, 100mm for concrete, 100mm for longitudinal main reinforcement, 100mm for stirrups were provided in order to avoid the distortion of elements.

Fig 5: Finite Element Model and Analysis Details

Results and Discussions

The Load-Displacement graph was compared. FEM is a suite of powerful engineering simulation programs, based on the finite element method, which can solve problems ranging from relatively simple linear analyses to the most challenging nonlinear simulations. It can simulate real time structural engineering problems and gives most accurate results w.r.t reinforced concrete was used for numerical modelling and evaluation.

Table 1: Experimental and FEM Results of Impacted RC Columns

Specimen Name	No. of impacts	Axial Capacity Experimental [kN]	Displacement experimental [mm]	Axial Capacity Analytical [kN]	Displacement Analytical [mm]
C-1-0-1	0	772	2.5	627	1.28
C-2-0-2	0	764	1.216	627	1.28
C-3-0-3	0	760	3.06	627	1.28
C-4-0-4	0	711	2.795	627	1.28
C-1-HLC-8	18	750	1.5	616	1.3
C-2-HLC-16	19	716	2.52	586	1.19
C-3-HLC-18	23	702	1.28	578	1.31
C-1-MIC-18	8	684	1.245	571	1.40
C-2-MIC-19	16	684	1.45	564	1.40
C-3-MIC-23	19	640	1.28	564	1.21
C-1-MAC-23	23	646	1.75	553	1.18
C-2-MAC-28	28	637	1.676	528	1.19
C-3-MAC-28	28	620	1.2	497	0.99
C-1-S-25	25	596	1.336	497	0.99
C-2-S-28	28	591	2.011	467	1.40

C-3-S-29	29	574	0.96	466	0.82
C-1-SD-29	29	559	1.66	452	1
C-2-SD-30	30	529	0.75	448	1.15
C-3-SD-31	31	501	0.838	418	1.08
C-4-SD-34	34	494	0.95	253	1.41

Fig 6: Simulation Envelopes of Severely Damaged RC Columns by Impact Loads Followed by Axial Compression

Fig 7: Load vs Displacement Graph for Impacted RC Columns. Comparison Between Experimental and Analytical

Fig 8: Load vs Displacement Graph for Impacted RC Columns. Comparison Between Experimental and Analytical

Conclusions

1. Experimental determination of average percentage reduction of RC Columns damaged by repetitive impacts were 3.87%, 10.96%, 15.62%, 21.92%, 30.73% respectively for hairline, minor, major cracks, spalling and severe damage.
2. Experimental determination of average reduced axial capacity of RC Columns damaged by repetitive impacts were 29kN, 82kN, 117kN, 165kN, 231kN for hairline, minor, major cracks, spalling and severe damage respectively.
3. The numerical determination of average percentage reduction of RC Columns damaged by repetitive impacts were 5.37%, 9.68%, 16.11%, 23.98%, 37.36% respectively for hairline, minor, major cracks, spalling and severe damage.
4. From the study it is clear that on an average a mass of spherical weight of 8kg with velocity of 70m/s, 100m/s, 100m/s, 132m/s, 137m/s, 155m/s is well enough to induce the damage hairline crack, Minor crack, Major crack, Spalling of concrete, Severe damage for the RC Column. These velocities during the time of impact may be the cumulative of the repetitive impacts or causes damage during the single impact.
5. The possibility for the impact load at the buildings RC Column are fall away of the nearby buildings during the earthquake event. The impact caused by rock fall during a landslide. The impacts are highly intensive which may cause overall collapse of the building at the very first impact.
6. The structural axial capacity of RC Columns damaged till hair line cracks and minor cracks behave similarly. It was confirmed from the experimental and analytical investigation. As well as the capacities of the RC Columns damaged till spalling and severe damage exhibits similar reduction in the load carrying capacity.
7. It can be best concluded that RC Column under low velocity light mass repetitive impact will significantly suffer high damage level as these columns does not design for the impact load
8. The existing RC Columns should be properly strengthened against repetitive loads. Importance should be given for the buildings low sotrey parking columns.

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